

Proposed Marketing Communications Strategy for a New Fighting Brand: A Case Study for SIG

Irma Oktarini¹, Neneng Nurlaela Arief², Iwan Setiawan³

^{1,2,3} School of Business Management, Bandung Institute of Technology, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study investigates the launch of a fighting brand in the cement industry, focusing on the challenges faced by a market-leading company with an existing flagship brand amidst emerging economical players. The goal is to enable the fighting brand to compete aggressively while avoiding cannibalization of the flagship brand, thus maintaining market leadership. Using a qualitative approach, primary data were collected through semi-structured interviews with internal informants, small contractors, and heads of masons, while secondary data came from the latest Brand Equity Index report of 2023.

Key findings reveal that masons equate price with quality and prefer application-based cement for profitability. Differentiation is crucial to minimize cannibalization risks. The study proposes a new target for the fighting brand with detailed psychographics and behavior, aiming for a targeted marketing strategy and communication. Insights for communication management and marketing are provided, suggesting marketing activities based on the 5A model to ensure successful brand management. The study offers new perspectives for the company and the cement industry, emphasizing the importance of a multi-brand strategy to address future challenges.

KEYWORDS: Fighting brand, cannibalization, 5A Model, targeted marketing communication, cement industry, brand management, multi-brand strategy, marketing strategy.

INTRODUCTION

The Indonesian cement market has grown due to economic development, a growing middle class, urbanization, and government-led infrastructure projects, with increased budget allocations supporting this growth. However, overcapacity has led to a competitive environment and declining utilization rates. The market features a two-tier pricing system: premium-priced cement from major players like SIG Group (with brands SG, DYX in Java island) and TR, and low-priced cement from eco-player brands like BIM and SGM, benefiting major players but causing price volatility.

Pricing strategies are localized, with high brand recognition allowing higher prices, while new brands use low-price strategies. SIG as cement leader company employs a multi-brand strategy to maintain dominance, but the rise of eco-brands has boosted the price-conscious segment, driven by cost-focused contractors, while homeowners prioritize quality over cost.

The Indonesian cement industry is facing severe price competition, with an average production utilization rate of 55% and significant pressure on profit margins due to intense rivalry. Tier-1 players, known for commanding higher prices due to strong brand recognition, are particularly affected, while tier-2 and eco-brand manufacturers employ aggressive price strategies to gain market share.

In response, SIG, launch a "fighting brand" role, to counter eco-brands and retain market share. This involves using established brands from other area outside Java "SP cement" in new roles, which can create market confusion and affect brand image due to inconsistent positioning, since SP is a premium brand in Sumatra. Recently SIG launched new Fighting Brand called MDK, with initial objective is to replace existing Fighting Brand. In Java, MDK was meant to replace SP. Now, MDK is still in introduction / launching phase.

Companies must adapt by revising pricing strategies, exploring cost-reduction measures, and investing in product innovation to attract customers beyond price considerations. The challenge is to develop an effective communication strategy for the fighting brand, targeting masons while minimizing risks of cannibalization and market confusion.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Segmenting, Targeting, Positioning & Differentiation -Brand

The STP Marketing Framework is a three-step method for developing targeted marketing strategies by segmenting, targeting, and positioning an offering (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018). Segmentation involves dividing the market into smaller groups with similar

characteristics using techniques like surveys and customer data analysis. Targeting assesses these segments based on profitability, size, growth potential, competition, and alignment with company goals to determine where to focus marketing efforts. Positioning creates a distinct perception in the target customers' minds by highlighting the product's unique value proposition. Additionally, the ST & PDB Triangle (Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning, Differentiation, and Brand) by Kartajaya emphasizes the interconnectedness of these elements for building a strong brand. Effective differentiation supports positioning and brand integrity, essential for establishing a strong and recognizable identity that aligns with the brand, ultimately leading to strong brand equity.

B. Marketing Mix (4P's)

Introduced by E. Jerome McCarthy in 1960, outlines four key components for effectively promoting a product or service: Product, Price, Place, and Promotion. The Product refers to the goods or services offered, including their design, features, and quality. Price is the amount customers pay, influenced by production costs, market conditions, and perceived value. Place ensures products are accessible to customers through strategic distribution channels. Promotion encompasses activities to communicate product benefits and persuade purchases, including advertising and digital marketing. This framework helps companies tailor their strategies to meet customer needs and achieve marketing objectives.

C. Porter 5 Forces

Porter's Five Forces is a strategic model used to evaluate the competitive landscape of an industry, considering factors beyond just existing competitors. Introduced by Michael E. Porter in his Harvard Business Review article, the model assesses five key forces that influence market desirability and profitability:

1. **Threat of New Entrants:** The ease with which new companies can enter the industry, influenced by factors like high capital costs, customer loyalty, government regulations, and economies of scale.
2. **Bargaining Power of Suppliers:** The power suppliers have over companies, especially when they control crucial resources or have few alternatives for buyers.
3. **Bargaining Power of Customers:** The influence buyers have on pricing and terms, particularly when they make large purchases or can easily switch to other products.
4. **Threat of Substitutes:** The availability of alternative products that can replace the industry's offerings, which can limit prices and attract customers away.
5. **Competitor Rivalry:** The level of competition among existing players, affected by market size, product differentiation, and the number of competitors.

By analyzing these forces, organizations can better understand their competitive environment and develop strategies to improve profitability and gain a competitive advantage.

D. Types of Buying Decision Behaviors

Understanding consumer purchasing behavior is pivotal for businesses aiming to create effective marketing strategies. By delving into the complexities of how consumers make purchasing decisions, companies can tailor their offerings to meet customer needs and preferences. Factors such as culture, social influences, personal values, and psychological states significantly impact these choices. Kotler and Armstrong's framework categorizes buying behavior based on involvement and brand differentiation, providing valuable insights for marketers to segment their target audience and develop tailored strategies.

Consumer buying behavior is influenced by factors such as product complexity, perceived risk, and brand familiarity. High-involvement purchases with significant brand differences lead to complex buying behavior, while low-involvement purchases with minimal brand differences result in habitual buying behavior. Dissonance-reducing buying behavior occurs when consumers face high involvement but limited brand options, leading to post-purchase anxiety. Variety-seeking behavior is characterized by low involvement but a desire for new experiences, prompting brand switching. Understanding these patterns helps marketers tailor strategies effectively.

	High involvement	Low involvement
Significant differences between brands	Complex buying behavior	Variety-seeking buying behavior
Few differences between brands	Dissonance-reducing buying behavior	Habitual buying behavior

Types of Buying Decision Behavior (Source: Kotler & Armstrong 2017)

Consumer buying behavior is influenced by several factors Cultural Factors, Social Factors, Personal Factors, and Psychological Factors. Understanding these aspects allows companies to develop well-rounded marketing strategies that address customer needs and achieve business goals.

E. 5A’s Framework

The customer path encompasses all interactions with consumers from the initial discovery of a product or service to the decision to recommend it to others. This lifecycle includes five key phases, known as the 5A model (Aware, Appeal, Ask, Act, Advocate), as defined by Kotler, Kartajaya, and Setiawan (2017). Here’s a summary of each phase:

1. **Aware:** Potential customers first learn about the brand through marketing, social media, word-of-mouth, or in-store encounters.
2. **Appeal:** After becoming aware, consumers show interest in the brand by researching it online, visiting the website, or reading reviews.
3. **Ask:** Genuinely interested consumers seek more information by contacting customer support, asking questions on social media, or comparing the product with competitors.
4. **Act:** Customers make a decision, such as purchasing the product, signing up for a trial, or subscribing to a service. Ensuring a smooth transaction is crucial here.
5. **Advocate:** Satisfied customers may become advocates by recommending the brand to others, writing positive reviews, or becoming repeat buyers.

By understanding these stages, brands can create targeted marketing strategies to attract new customers, nurture leads, and convert them into loyal advocates.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher will employ a qualitative research methodology to investigate the research topic. Both primary and secondary data will be collected to ensure comprehensive data analysis. The primary data collection method will involve semi-structured interviews with key internal personnel selected based on their experience, expertise, and current roles within the company. This approach aims to gather in-depth insights into the research problem.

Internal source : To gather the insight, Semi-structured interviews are applied, using topic guides with key questions asked uniformly in every sub-interview. These questions are designed to be open-ended, encouraging interviewees to provide more detailed responses rather than just yes or no answers. Below is the initial question list for internal informants.

External Source : To gain a more holistic insight, the author also conducted interviews with users of the new MDK cement product with specific target respondent Mason on construction phase using MDK cement. The interview conducted in face to face, both using video call and offline method. Below is the initial question list for external customers, the questions adapted from Mahapatra, 2019.

To derive valuable insights and arrive at well-informed conclusions, data gathering analysis includes classifying, processing, organizing, and evaluating the gathered data is performed. Content analysis approaches were employed in most of the data analysis

methods in this study to Identify patterns based on respondents' insights and profiles. Following that, the data and responses from the respondents will be analyzed in accordance with the requirements of the research's goals.

FINDINGS & ANALYSIS

This chapter presents the key findings from both internal and external analysis to address the research question. The findings are then translated into the actionable solutions that can be implemented.

A. CUSTOMERS IN CEMENT DECISION MAKING

Consumers see cement as a simple commodity with minimal brand differentiation, primarily focused on durability, strength, and protection. Cement is a key purchase in home building, often determining the retail shop where other construction materials are bought.

Illustration of relationships of all parties

The home-building process involves several key parties: the homeowner, who pays and relies on close contacts and experts for decisions; the head of mason or contractor, who guides the homeowner and often decides the cement brand; the retailer, who facilitates the process and keeps pace with pricing; and the architect, who influences both the homeowner and mason but rarely specifies a brand. Marketing communication should target both homeowners and masons, as they play significant roles in making purchase decisions.

B. INTERNAL ANALYSIS

• Current STP- Differentiation – Brand

Segmentation in the retail cement category involves dividing the market into distinct consumer groups based on demographics, geography, psychographics, behavior, and usage. For SIG brands in Java, the key segments are:

- Demographic Segmentation:
 - Homeowners: Middle-aged individuals (25-55 years) likely to undertake home renovations or new constructions.
 - Masons: Professionals aged 30-60 in the construction industry with a consistent income from projects.
- Geographic Segmentation:
 - Focus on urban and rural areas in Java with a significant emphasis on residential houses.
 - Regional preferences influence cement brand choices due to distribution factors and product age affecting quality.
- Psychographic Segmentation:
 - Quality-Conscious Buyers: Those prioritizing durability and strength, willing to pay a premium.
 - Cost-Conscious Buyers: Those seeking the most economical options.
- Behavioral Segmentation:
 - Homeowners:
 - Those influenced by brand reputation and quality.
 - Those driven by cost-effectiveness.
 - Masons:
 - Brand Loyalists: Consistently purchase specific brands due to positive experiences.
 - Switchers: May switch brands based on price or availability.
- Usage Purpose Segmentation:
 - Segmented by building type into simple houses, single houses, and medium-rise housing, each with specific sub-segments and key drivers.

• **Current Situation & Internal Perspective**

According to an internal analysis on market acceptance, distributors have largely welcomed the new cement brand, MDK, but seek assurance on strategy, particularly regarding price stability and stock availability. Central Java shows the most progressive growth and distributor confidence, while East Java requires improved channel management and distributor support. Retail acceptance is positive, driven by competitive pricing and endorsements from the main brand, though some retailers perceive MDK as comparable to SP cement rather than the main brand, SG Cement. Suggestions for improvement include emphasizing MDK's quality, maintaining competitive pricing without sudden increases, enhancing communication and branding to boost awareness, and ensuring main brand support to reinforce premium positioning. Packaging quality in East Java also needs attention.

• **Marketing Mix MDK (4P's)**

SIG's marketing strategy for the fighting brand MDK uses the 4Ps framework to ensure accessibility and preference among consumers.

Product: MDK cement is a multipurpose cement available in 40 and 50 kg packaging, conforming to the latest standards and suitable for both structural and non-structural use. It features smooth mixing, optimal drying time, and good workability. The packaging is like SG Cement, with regional endorsements from main brands like DYX to facilitate market acceptance.

Place: MDK cement targets regions with aggressive eco-players, primarily in Java, with plans to expand further. It is distributed through traditional retailers, with around 25,000 retailers in Java out of 40,000 nationwide.

Price: The pricing of MDK cement varies by region, set at or slightly below the price of the next best competitor to accelerate market penetration. It is also priced lower than SP cement as part of a transition strategy.

Promotion: During the launch phase, MDK cement is promoted through point-of-sale materials like posters, brochures, and merchandise, with minimal advertising budget. The brand is also featured on the SIG website and social media for awareness.

• **VRIO Analysis**

To evaluate Fighting Brand role, MDK competitiveness in relation to business process and advantages, author developed the following primary outline using the VRIO framework:

Resource or Capability	Valuable	Rare	Imitability	Organized to Capture Value	Competitive Advantage
Most competent company in the industry	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Temporary Competitive Advantage
Supply chain & distribution channel	Yes	Yes	No	-	Temporary Competitive Advantage
Good product quality	Yes	No	-	-	Competitive Parity
Continuous Product Development	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Temporary Competitive Advantage
Good value for money	Yes	No	-	-	Competitive Parity
Targeted Market product	Yes	Yes	No	-	Temporary Competitive Advantage

C. EXTERNAL ANALYSIS

• **Porter 5 Forces**

To analyze the external environment of SIG's cement brands, Porter's Five Forces framework is applied:

The Indonesian cement market faces several key competitive forces:

1. **Threat of New Entrants:** Low due to government restrictions on new permits and high investment costs.
2. **Bargaining Power of Suppliers:** Medium to high, primarily because of the reliance on coal and its rising prices, despite abundant raw materials.

3. **Bargaining Power of Customers:** High, as cement is seen as a low-differentiation commodity with many available brands, making customers price-sensitive.
 4. **Competitive Rivalry:** Very high, driven by market overcapacity and many brands competing aggressively on price.
 5. **Threat of Substitutes:** Low, as there are no direct substitutes for cement, even though instant mortar is gaining popularity.
- Given this highly competitive and price-sensitive environment, companies should:

- Increase the use of alternative fuels to reduce coal dependency.
- Innovate and secure distribution channels to differentiate beyond price.
- Foster strong brand loyalty, especially among regular buyers like masons.
- Develop derivative products to address customer needs and stand out from competitors.

• **PESTEL**

- **Political:** The Indonesian government's increased infrastructure budget for 2024, rising by 5% from 2023, reflects the country's rapid population and economic growth. However, the cement industry faces challenges in adhering to sustainable practices due to new ecological regulations from the Ministry of Public Works and Housing.
- **Economic:** Indonesia's consistent GDP growth, averaging around 5% annually over the past decade, positions it as a key emerging economy with a growing middle class and significant investments in infrastructure and manufacturing.
- **Socio-Cultural:** Rapid urbanization in Indonesia, with 60% of the population expected to live in urban areas by 2023, is driving demand for cement due to increased residential, commercial, and public construction projects. Government investments in infrastructure further boost cement consumption.
- **Technological:** High and rising internet usage among Indonesians, including masons who use online resources for tutorials, networking, and purchasing materials, is contributing to improved business growth. However, digital literacy varies, requiring continuous efforts to bridge the digital divide, especially in rural areas.
- **Ecological:** The Indonesian government aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 29% by 2030 through efforts within the cement industry, which has already shown progress by reducing emissions intensity from 725.66 kg CO₂/ton in 2010 to 641.5 kg CO₂/ton in 2020.
- **Legal:** The cement industry must comply with various laws and regulations, including maintaining a Quality Management System based on SNI ISO 9001:2015 standards and adhering to labor laws. These legal requirements are dynamic and can significantly influence market conditions and competition.

• **Competitor Analysis**

Author analyzes the competitors based on company and brands as follows :

1. IDCMT produce 4 cement brands :
 - a. TR

Product	TR cement is the flagship brand IDCMT using PCC- SNI 7064:2014 already established for 40 years and known for good quality.
Place	Available nationally around Indonesia, through traditional retail channel. On Sept 2022, collaborates with BSW cement. This collaboration was carried out under a scheme to rent a place to support production in Eastern Indonesia.
Price	Mostly charge premium price and play around premium league. Charge higher in its strong market area - eg Western Java. Price around 55.000 – 63.000 rupiah in strong area.
Promotion	Focus on Trade Promo for retail ; Loyalty Program with Mitra Semen TR Program (MSTR). Create engagement through social media, Instagram as a main channel, while Tiktok, FB and youtube content are mirroring. Mason activities like mason training, also content and quiz in social media also.

b. RJWL

Product	On 2016, IDCMT launch new economical product RJWL cement, using different SNI product, PPC -SNI 0302-2014
Place	Available mostly in Java. Strong area is Banten & West Java.
Price	Range depends on area and competition. But in average RJWL maintain lower price gap with its premium brand in range 9000-15000 rupiah
Promotion	Establish social media channel with mason through official IG & Tiktok account, actively post short video about mason daily life and quiz.

c. JMPL

January 2023, JMPL cement was launched using two SNI , PCC- SNI 7064:2014 and PPC -SNI 0302-2014. Up to now distributed in limited area where there is fierce competition such as Banten & Cirebon . Maintain its price gap with RJWL lower in range 4000-5000 rupiah. There is minimum support on communication for this product.

d. GRB

In October 2023, GRB cement (local player in central Java) was acquired 100% by IDCMT and become one group. This product using PCC -SNI 7064-2014. Price range between 40.000 to 48.000 for 40kg size. GRB has active social media content in Instagram, facebook and tiktok and minimum local media campaign.

2. STA produce 1 cement brands

a. BMA

Product	As a flagship brand, BMA using different SNI compared to others, which is PCC- SNI 0302:2004, while this is outdated. BMA launch its first product around 2012-1013.
Place	Mainly focus on Central Java but have some expansion to other part of Java near the plant.
Price	Positioning the product as premium, with justification using PCC. Price range still in economical product in 47.000 – 53.000 in strong area.
Promotion	Mostly focus on Retailer to push product into market. Mason activities and local advertising also done in local area. Approaching its target market with female figure in every communication.

3. SIA produce 2 cement brands

a. SM:

Product	As a flagship product, SM using typical PCC SNI 7064:2014. Claimed as a high strength and use less water in its application.
Place	Since the plant is located in East Java, so the main focus also there. Started production in 2020. Holding group plan to expand its plant to Aceh, Kalimantan & Nusa Tenggara.
Price	As a new entrant in economical arena, SM positioned its price very low in range 30.000-45.000 to accelerate penetration to the market.
Promotion	As a typical eco-product, mostly focus on retail with discount & cashback. During launch period they have 1 billboard near airport.

b. SII :

Product	Using same SNI product as SM, packaging logo similar to SIG cement brands, circle with red and black color. Act as a fighting brand role from the company
Place	Same area focuses with SM, but aggressive in near plant area
Price	As a fighting brand, the price is very low, maintain its price gap with the flagship brand around 4000-5000 rupiah.
Promotion	Minimum support on promotion, since the price already very low.

• **Consumer Analysis**

To get deeper understanding about Psychographic, attitude and behaviour of mason towards cement brand 10 masons were interviewed across Java, with 3 main themes; Construction process to get to know about the pain points and important factors; Buying decision process and last is about MDK brand. Below is the summary of first theme.

Theme	Initial Question	Answers
Screening : Mason (Contractor / Head of Mason), Decision Maker, MDK user in a construction		
Construction process	How to get the project ?	Previous client Through Word of Mouth My friends, relatives or former boss Sometimes "Facebook"
	How are the steps to conduct and execute project, who decide the cement brand?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning - <i>"here include design, RAB & price negotiation"</i> • Buying process, started with find Source / retail and other materials. Basic material like cement, sand, iron buy in traditional retail store. Some respondents in urban buy finishing material in modern store. <i>"For ceramics, I go to depo bangunan because of the discount"</i> • Execution of Construction
	What are the challenges in construction process ?	<i>"In the beginning of the process is price negotiation"</i> <i>"Sometimes difficult to find worker"</i> Availability of building material, Time management also play key roles
	What are the important factors in construction ?	<i>"How to balance client satisfaction and construction budget"</i> According to RAB, Price Negotiation, Good result. Good and skilled worker

From the second theme about price question, indicates that mason also define that there are “premium players” and “eco-players”, and assume that premium product has better quality than the eco player. From this question there are some indications that they try to push brand that give them benefit. Respondents do not hesitate to use two brands for different application stage, to give him maximum benefit.

On the next theme about MDK, source of awareness coming from Retail store, respondents interested to try MDK because of the affordable price, also some of them see endorsement logo from main brand as a trusted stamp for this new product. This also indicates that respondents are people who’s not afraid to try new product if it is qualified with basic factor for cement.

D. SWOT ANALYSIS

Based on the analysis above, author can conclude SWOT analysis for MDK cement brand as follows :

Strengths:

- MDK cement is backed by a reputable company with proven products like SG cement and DYX cement, enhancing its credibility.
- Targets diverse customer segments, meeting various needs and preferences.
- Extensive distribution network facilitates market penetration.
- First brand to use new SNI, producing a less carbon-intensive product, enhancing cost efficiency.
- Competitive pricing makes MDK cement appealing to consumers.

Weaknesses:

- Low support for marketing activities and end-user promotions, focusing mainly on distributor and retail programs with minimal pull activities.
- Increased operational complexity due to managing multiple brands and maintaining consistent messaging.
- Risk of brand cannibalization, leading to internal competition and reduced market share.
- MDK cement has lower margins compared to other cement bag products in SIG.

Opportunities:

- High government spending on infrastructure boosts potential cement demand.
- Cross-selling opportunities among eco-brands in different categories to enhance overall sales.
- Digitalization offers new channels to connect with project owners and access to financial decision-makers.
- Social media usage among masons provides a platform for communication, information, and entertainment.

Threats:

- Multi-brand strategy is easily replicable by competitors.
- Potential for price wars as eco-players might use pricing as a primary market penetration strategy.
- New SNI, once issued, can be adopted by competitors after development time.
- Market acceptance challenges due to the new SNI, which may create perceptions of insufficient product strength for buildings over two stories.

BUSINESS SOLUTION

A. PROPOSED NEW TARGETING & POSITIONING

SIG’s cement brands should clearly differentiate the target focus for its Main Brand and Fighting Brand. The author suggests a new matrix for the target audience in marketing communications. For masons, based on the analysis and qualitative research on existing customers of cement MDK, a new target segment is proposed.

Target Segment	Brand Role : Fighting Brand
	MDK
Regional / Geographical	All Java Island, specifically targeted to Eco player area and specific retailer which sells Next best competitor (target).
Demographic Mason	Gender: Male Age: 30-60 years old Education: High School for Mason, University for Contractors Status: With family & Single Social Class: Middle to Low
Psychographic Mason	Budget Savvy Open minded, curious, business focused and willing to explore alternatives. Often driven by the desire to find better options, or unique features. Smart and seeks efficiency that can give him maximum returns.
Behavioral Mason	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decide the cement brand. • Availability is the most important factor toward cement brand decision making, followed by quality and price (as long as the quality equal to others and has standard-SNI) • Using payment system all services includes labor & material. • Will try to push brands giving him maximum returns, seeks efficiency. • Not hesitate to use multi brand in his projects (Premium brand for structural work, Eco-brand for Masonry work)

B. PROPOSED DIFFERENTIATION USING MARKETING MIX 4P’s

After establishing differentiation among eco-players, it is crucial to develop distinct differentiation against the main or complementary brands to reduce the risk of cannibalization. The author proposed a different focus.

Role Brand	Main /Complementary Brand		Fighting Brand
Brand	SG	DYX	MDK
Homeowner Target	Harmonizer	Discerning	-
Mason Target	Pious Religious	Achievers go getter	Budget Savvy

According to literature review of decision buying behavior masons typically exhibit habitual buying behavior for cement products, while homeowners display dissonance-reducing buying behavior due to the infrequent and risky nature of building a house, along with minimal brand differences. To enhance homeowner involvement, brands should create urgency through educational efforts. Thus:

- For dissonance-reducing buying behavior: Implement after-sale communication and service to minimize dissonance.
- For habitual buying behavior: Focus on product enhancement and consistent advertising to reinforce consumer habits. The table below illustrates the proposed differentiation applied to the marketing mix 4P's.

4P's	Fighting Brand: MDK	Main Brand & Complementary: SG/ DYX
Product	Will apply new SNI after issued Max usage : 2 story houses	Existing SNI PCC 2014
	Woven packaging (more economical)	Kraft Packaging
	Accessible customer support during business hours	24/7 Technical Support through WA/Phone
Place	Spread throughout Java island, targeted specific to retail sells eco brand competitors (sniper mode) Channel : Traditional Retail	Quality Assurance, if the cement is stoned before its expired time
	Spread throughout Java island, targeted specific to retail sells eco brand competitors (sniper mode) Channel : Traditional Retail	Spread throughout Java island, massive Availability Channel : Traditional Retail, Online through SB service (owned digital channel, directly to Homeowner. Provide service to renovate or build house)
Price	At par with Next Best Competitor of Eco in targeted area. Potential increased price from current condition after introduction period. DKI-Banten: RJWL DIY-Jateng: GRB Jatim-Bali: SM	- Maintain optimum price, in accordance with willingness to pay - Maintain optimum Disparity with Next best Competitor (mainly TR)
Promotion	Budget Adv +	Budget Adv ++
	Communication Focus on mason about guidance and tips to optimized project	Communication and education to Homeowner about the importance of high-quality building material
		Communication on mason focus on empowerment

C. PROPOSED MARKETING ACTIVITIES USING 5A FRAMEWORK

Using the 5A framework, the author proposed the following marketing activities for MDK cement and suggestions for differentiating the main brand:

1. **Aware:** Create brand awareness through targeted advertising with simple banners directing customers to retail stores and maintaining a social media presence by sharing content and promotions in existing mason communities on WhatsApp and Facebook.
2. **Appeal:** Make the brand attractive by highlighting cost-effectiveness and competitive pricing, developing a relatable brand personality for budget-conscious consumers, and sharing user testimonials from contractors and masons.
3. **Ask:** Encourage customers to seek more information by providing educational content at local mason gatherings, offering guidelines and tips for optimal use, and scheduling basic training programs to encourage product trials.

4. Act: Streamline the purchasing decision by ensuring product availability in targeted retail locations and offering promotions for first-time buyers, such as flexible payment terms or free product samples.
5. Advocate: Turn customers into brand advocates by rewarding masons who share their experiences and tips on social media or within their communities, fostering loyalty and advocacy.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that MDK cement, as a fighting brand, should target budget-savvy masons and minimalist budget-conscious homeowners, emphasizing the importance of understanding consumer psychographics. The brand's positioning should align with the budget-savvy segment's expectations of availability, price, and quality, placing it in the eco-player quadrant to maintain market share without diluting the premium brand. Distributors and retailers play a crucial role in the brand's success, with positive initial responses but suggestions for improvement in product highlights, packaging, and price consistency. Marketing activities for MDK cement launch, beginning in May 2024, will vary by region, allowing the brand to aggressively counter eco-brand competitors and adjust its presence based on competition, as detailed in proposed marketing activities.

RECOMMENDATION

The study identifies weaknesses and limitations in data scope and research, suggesting improvements such as expanding the study area, using additional instruments, and conducting detailed analyses with larger data sets. Recommendations for future research include exploring new high-margin products, particularly in masonry, developing strong marketing and integrated communication strategies for MDK cement, conducting post-launch studies to evaluate product success and market impact, and developing secured channels for the main brand to enhance competitive advantage. SIG's existing online platform, caller SB, can be utilized for direct access to building materials, while partnerships with digital ecosystem startups or established construction platforms can further strengthen this approach. The main brand should focus on homeowner engagement, creating emotional connections and credibility, while the fighting brand targets communication towards masons.

REFERENCES

1. Creswell, J. W., Creswell, J. D., (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed method approaches* 6ed. Sage Publications
2. Kotler, P., Armstrong, G, (2018), *Principles of Marketing* 17ed, Pearson.
3. Keller, & Swaminathan. (2020). *Strategic Brand Management Building, Measuring, and Managing Brand Equity* (5th ed.). Pearson.
4. Kotler, Kertajaya, & Setiawan. (2010). *Marketing 3.0 Moving from Traditional to Digital*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc
5. Kotler, Kertajaya, & Setiawan. (2017). *Marketing 4.0 Moving from Traditional to Digital*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc
6. Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). *Marketing Management* (15th ed.). Pearson.
7. Porter, Michael E., 2008, *The Five Competitive Forces that Shape Strategy*. Harvard Business Review, pp.79.

Cite this Article: Irma Oktarini, Neneng Nurlaela Arief, Iwan Setiawan (2024). Proposed Marketing Communications Strategy for a New Fighting Brand: A Case Study for SIG. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 7(8), 5952-5962